

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND COMMITMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL COUNSELLORS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school Counsellors in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted by the researcher. A total of 188 secondary school Counsellors formed the population of the study. Findings from the study showed among others, that secondary school Counsellors in Anambra State are satisfied and committed to their job. The researcher made some recommendations which include; designing counselling job in such a way that it will be more challenging for counsellors to take responsibilities of their job outcomes.

Keywords: job commitment, job satisfaction, relationship, school counsellors

Introduction

In today's competitive world every organization faces new challenges as regards sustained productivity and creating committed workforce. No organization therefore can perform at peak level unless each employee is committed to the organizations objectives. The extent to which an employee's motives or needs are met in the work place impact so much on the employee's work behaviour Al-Ajimi, (2006). How employees feel about the work they are doing and the results received from that work directly impact on their performance and their job satisfaction (Coleman and Cooper, 2008).

Job satisfaction according to Coetzee, Schreuder and Thadinyane (2007) is an individual's total feeling about his/her job and attitudes he/she has towards various

aspects or facets of his/her job, as well as an attitude and perception that could consequently influence the degree of fit between the individual and the organization. Kaldenberg, Becker & Zuvonkovic (2009) see job satisfaction as the result of individuals' perception and evaluation of their job influenced by their own unique values, needs and expectations, which they regard as being important to them.

Baron & Greenberg, (2005), nevertheless contend that job satisfaction among employees is an indicator of organizational effectiveness, and it is influenced by organizational and personal factors such as organisational commitment to set goals, workers incentives, job involvement, job commitment, and job satisfaction. Most employers realize that the optimal functioning of their organization depends in part on the level of job satisfaction of employees, hence the emergence of the statement, satisfied employees are happy employees, happy employees are productive and successful (Riggio, 2009). For performance to be optimal, an employee's full potential is needed at all levels in organization. In other words, employees who are dissatisfied are likely to be less committed and less productive.

Job commitment according to Ayers (2008) is a measurable degree of an employee's positive or negative emotional attachment to their job, colleagues and organization which profoundly influences their willingness to learn and perform at work. Armstrong (2009) sees job commitment as occurring when people at work are interested or positively excited about their jobs and are prepared to go extra mile to get them done to the best of their ability.

Murphy (2004) sees job commitment as characterized by attitude and behaviour, while Kelton (2010) describes an attitude as evaluative statements or judgments – either favourable or unfavourable – concerning a phenomenon. In view of the above, employees who evaluate or perceive their job favourably, that is, in terms of meeting their needs tend to engage in behaviours that foster or support it, and employees who evaluate their job unfavourably tend to engage in behaviours that hinder or oppose it Coleman & Cooper, (2008). From the above logic, employees' attitude to their job should be related to their behaviours on the job, the most central of which is commitment to the job. Committed employees are likely to manifest positive behaviour towards their job. They are more likely to perform beyond the call of duty to meet the clients' needs and the demands of the entire society.

On relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment

Job satisfaction and job commitment appear to be two most commonly studied job related attitudes. Though the two concepts are different, they appear to be highly

correlated and result in similar employee behaviour. According to Falkenburg & Sychyns (2007), a strong correlation has been empirically established between job satisfaction and employees commitment. Researches show that satisfied employees tend to be committed to their job/organization Cooper, Hakim & Viewsvaran, (2005) and employees who are satisfied and committed are more likely to attend work Lumley (2010), stay with an organisation Zimmerman & Damold (2009) arrive at work on time Burke & Greenglass, (2005) perform well at work and engage in behaviour helpful to the organization Thomas & Tymon, (2007) than are employees who are not satisfied and committed.

Siti (2010) had a similar opinion when he argued that employees with higher job satisfaction are more likely to increase their commitment to the organization. However, the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment is not consistent across people or jobs. For example, for complex job, there is a stronger relationship between job satisfaction and commitment than for jobs of low or medium complexity (Thomas & Tymon, (2007).

School as an organization employs people in order to use them realize its own goals which include among others the production of intellectual and responsible human beings. The school like any other organization employs different categories of workers through whom it realizes its objectives; among such workers are school counsellors, teachers and others. A school counsellor is one who has innate and acquired skills for helping people who have problems to have deep insight into their own abilities and capabilities Okoye, Adejumo & Achebe, (2007).

School counsellor is responsible for the development and growth of students. More so, they play a large role in the overall development of students as intellectual and productive human beings. Such roles include among others; managing the organizational process that reflect the need of the school and its students; and preparing students through adjustments and skill development to match dynamic society of the day.

Ofodum (2004) observes that counsellors in Anambra State contend with myriads of problems in their career. These problems include lack of comfortable or attractive offices, irregular payment of emoluments and stringent funding. Ofodum notes that the conditions of counsellors were made worse by the compulsory assignment of teaching load and other bureaucracies and paper work in most schools. This is not only unprofessional but also impacts so heavily on the counsellors job satisfaction and their overall attitude to work.

Statt (2007) observes that poor attitude of counsellors to work not only frustrates students but also make them encounter such problems as poor study habit, inadequate

knowledge about proper subject combination, poor foundation for life-long career development, poor transition from education to labour market among others. Stratt further notes that these problems, if not properly resolved culminates into various misbehaviours such as dropping out of school, truancy, examination malpractices, drug addiction, cultism, sexual promiscuity and premature pregnancy. This shows that school counsellors who manifest poor or negative attitude as a result of low level of job satisfaction are likely to produce less result-oriented outcomes.

Nevertheless, school counsellors no matter their age or gender need some kind of motivation to experience job satisfaction. Obikeze, Obi and Abonyi (2005) define motivation as the act of directing an individual's behaviour towards a particular end through the manipulation of incentives. When workers are properly motivated they tend to be satisfied and more likely to produce result-oriented outcomes. But where they are not satisfied as a result of inadequate motivation, they are likely to be less committed to their work which in turn influences the organization's performance and ultimately its stability. Thus, it does appear that the level of commitment workers show to job depends largely on the level of satisfaction.

It therefore follows that organizations with low employee satisfaction is vulnerable to both internal and external challenges because its employees are not going the extra mile to increasing performance but ultimately under perform. This seems to be the case with school counsellors. Thus, it appears school counsellors who are less satisfied are likely to be less committed, but one cannot conclude for certain without empirical evidence.

The researcher therefore, is interested in finding the relationship between counsellors' job satisfaction and job commitment. Though, there are many studies on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance, there is relatively little or no research conducted on the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school counsellors in Anambra State, Nigeria.

The present work therefore is designated to determining the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school counsellors in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment of secondary school counsellors in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be significant to educational planners. Post-Primary School Services Commission (PPSSC), guidance counsellors, future researchers and the general public. The findings of this study will reveal to educational planners the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment of secondary school counsellors. It will also expose those factors that bring about job satisfaction which equally affect counsellors' job commitment. This knowledge will help the planners to eliminate sources of job dissatisfaction among counsellors with a view of improving their satisfaction. The result of this study will furnish the Post-Primary School Services Commission (PPSSC) with a range of information concerning those problems which affect counsellors' happiness and productivity. Such knowledge will instigate the commission to re-examine counsellors' programmes with a view of improving their satisfaction and commitment to duty. Guidance counsellors will find the result of this work beneficial since it will present them with the knowledge of the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment. This will serve as a base for improving counsellors overall performance.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How satisfied are the secondary school guidance counsellors in Anambra state, Nigeria?
2. How far are the secondary school counsellors in Anambra state commitment to their job in Anambra state, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between secondary school Guidance Counsellors' job satisfaction and their job commitment in Anambra state, Nigeria?

Method

The researcher adopted a correlational design. A correlational design is considered appropriate for this study because it seeks to establish a relationship between the two variables, namely, job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school counsellors in Anambra State, Nigeria.

There are six educational zones in Anambra, state and the population of the study comprises 188 counsellors from both public secondary schools and private schools in Anambra State. Public secondary schools have a total number of 145

counsellors (School Records, PPSSC: Awka 2013), while private secondary schools have a total number of 43 counsellors (School Records: PPSSC, Awka, 2013). Purposive sampling was employed in the selection of all the counsellors in Anambra state. The reason for the selection of all the 188 counsellors were based on the fact that the population is small and that there is no need to segregate the population since they share the same characteristics in their pattern of work.

The instrument is a questionnaire, named Job Satisfaction/Job Commitment Questionnaire (JSJCQ). The questionnaire was structured by the researcher using information from background of the study, research questions, and literature review. The instrument has two sections A and B. Section A contains personal data of the respondent while section B contains 24 items on job satisfaction- job commitment questionnaire (JSJCQ). It has 4 point response options which ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree and has weighted values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The researcher presented copies of the questionnaire together with purpose of the study, research questions to three experts, – two from Guidance and Counselling and one from Measurement and Evaluation all of whom are from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. The experts made a careful scrutiny of the items to ensure their appropriateness and adequacy as well as their relevance, clarity and language expression. The experts' constructive criticism and suggestions for modifying the instruments were considered. With the modification, the instrument was therefore deemed suitable for the study.

The researcher administered the instruments through direct delivery method, with the help of six trained research assistants. However, a total of 156 questionnaires representing 83% of the target sample was collected and used for the purpose of data analysis. The data collected from the research questions 1 – 2 were analysed using aggregate mean score. In measuring the counsellors' opinions, the Strongly agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly disagree statements were scaled in 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The mean of the scale is 2.50 which were used in dividing the aggregated scores into equivalent score for the job satisfaction and job commitment each measures which are as follows:

- 1.00 – 1.49 $\equiv$ 12.00–17.99 $\equiv$ Very Low (Satisfaction or
- 1.00 – 1.49 $\equiv$ 12.00–17.88 $\equiv$ Very Low (Satisfaction or Commitment)
- 1.50 – 2.49 $\equiv$ 18.00 – 29.88 $\equiv$ Low (Satisfaction or Commitment)
- 2.50 – 3.49 $\equiv$ 30.00 – 41.88 $\equiv$ High (Satisfaction or Commitment)
- 3.50 – 4.00 $\equiv$ 42.00 – 48.00 $\equiv$ Very High (Satisfaction or Commitment)

Research question 3 was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). This was used to determine if a relationship exist between job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school counsellors.

Results

Research Question One

How satisfied are the secondary school guidance counsellors in Anambra state?

Table 1: Table showing the Distribution of Secondary School Guidance Counsellors 'based on their Job Satisfaction levels

Levels	Range of scores	Frequency	Percentage
Very Low Satisfaction	12.00 – 17.99	0	0.0%
Low Satisfaction	18.00 – 29.99	15	9.6%
High Satisfaction	30.00 – 41.99	129	82.7%
Very High Satisfaction	42.00 – 48.00	12	7.7%
Total	12.00 – 48.00	156	100.0%

Table 1 revealed that the secondary school guidance counsellors in Anambra state have high satisfaction. The counsellors with high satisfaction constituted 82.7% which represents larger part of the guidance counsellors. In addition, the counsellors with very high satisfaction are 7.7% of 156. The result further shows that the guidance counsellors with very low satisfaction level is 0% while those with low satisfaction are 9.6%.

Research Question Two

How far are the secondary school counsellors in Anambra state commitment to their job?

Table 2: Table showing the Distribution of Secondary School Guidance Counsellors' based on their Job Commitment levels

Levels	Range of scores	Frequency	Percentage
Very Low Commitment	12.00 – 17.99	0	0.0%
Low Commitment	18.00 – 29.99	8	5.1%
High Commitment	30.00 – 41.99	135	86.5%
Very High Commitment	42.00 – 48.00	13	8.3%
Total	12.00 – 48.00	156	100.0%

Table 2 revealed that the secondary school counsellors in Anambra state have high commitment to their job. The counsellors with high commitment to their job constituted

86.5% which represents larger part of the guidance counsellors. In addition, the counsellors with very high commitment are 8.3% of 156. The result further shows that the guidance counsellors with very low commitment level are 0% and those with low satisfaction are 5.1%.

Research Question Three

What is the relationship between secondary school Guidance Counsellors' job satisfaction and their job commitment?

Table 3: Table showing the Relationship between Secondary School Guidance Counsellors' Job Satisfaction and their Job Commitment (N = 156)

Variables	Pearson Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)
Job Satisfaction score	0.287
Job Commitment score	

The result in Table 3 revealed that the relationship between the job satisfaction and the job commitment of the school counsellors is low and positive. The Pearson correlation coefficient (*r*) is 0.287 which indicates a low relationship. It is then concluded that there is low and positive correlation between secondary school guidance counsellors' job satisfaction and their job commitment.

Discussion of Results

The results of the study are discussed under the following subheadings:

- a. Job satisfaction of secondary school counsellors
- b. Job commitment of secondary school counsellors
- c. Relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment among secondary school counsellors.

Job satisfaction of Secondary School Guidance Counsellors

The findings from research question one revealed that majority of secondary school counsellors are job satisfied. This is in agreement with the earlier work by Franzway (2004) which revealed that Nigerian counsellors are satisfied with their job. However, satisfaction in a job does not occur in isolation but is dependent upon a number of factors. This is in consonant with the findings of Kelton (2010) on the predictors/determinants of job satisfaction which revealed some job-related factors such as work itself, recognition, career advancement, supervisory relationship, co-workers.

The findings of the study was also in line with similar studies conducted by Haggling (2005) and Hussin (2011) which also revealed that job satisfaction occurs as a result of some job-related factors.

Job Commitment of Secondary School Counsellors

The findings from research question two revealed that majority of Secondary School Guidance are committed to their job. The findings of this study was in line with the earlier work by Baker (2007) which revealed that school counsellors were committed to their job. This job commitment will continue in the future because the counsellors are not relenting in making a difference through the skills techniques they acquired from training.

Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Job Commitment among Secondary School Counsellors

The findings from research question three which sought to determine the relationship between job satisfaction and job commitment revealed a low positive relationship between the two variables. This result found support in previous study by Kimi (2006) which indicated a low positive association between job satisfaction and job commitment among school counsellors.

The findings of the study also revealed that significant relationship existed between school Guidance Counsellors job satisfaction and job commitment. This finding was in agreement with some other studies by Enanegs, (2005); Lumley, Coctzec, Thadinyane & Ferriera (2011), indicating that significant relationship existed between school counsellors job to satisfaction and their commitment. This relationship between Job Satisfaction and Job Commitment among Secondary School Counsellors will continue in the future because employees with high job satisfaction are likely to increase their commitment to the organisation as rightly noted by Siti,. (2010)

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concludes as follows:

- Majority of secondary school counsellors in Anambra State are happy and satisfied with their job and a greater number of counsellors are committed to their job.
- There is also low positive relationship between counsellor's job satisfaction and their job commitment.

- There is low positive relationship between older secondary school guidance counsellor's job satisfaction and their job commitment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher has proffered the following recommendations:

1. Since job satisfaction is dependent upon certain factors among which are the job itself, opportunity for advancement, recognition among others, management of Post Primary Schools should endeavour to design the counselling job in such a way that it will be more meaningful, interesting, challenging and offers counsellors opportunity to take the responsibilities of their job outcomes. This will ensure greater job satisfaction and devotion to performing task well.
2. Government or its agencies managing Post Primary Schools should periodically organize in-service education programmes such as conferences, workshop, seminars etc for counsellors to up-date their knowledge and enhance their proficiency on the job.

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